

Contribution of Mushrooms to Farm Income and the Socioeconomic Conditions Analysis of the Growers

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ABSTRACT

For the growth and production of agriculture, it is crucial to implement new technology. Farmers' adoption of the technology was influenced by their socioeconomic situation. Therefore, it is crucial to research the social standing of the farmer. Data from a survey of 60 farm homes served as the basis for the analysis. Using a straightforward random procedure, a sample was chosen from the list of mushroom growers. Based on the quantity of bags produced, all mushroom farmers were divided into three categories: Small Category (300), Medium Category (301–500), and Large Category (>500). The study's findings showed that every farmer and the majority of their families were literate. Studying households' literacy levels revealed that, on average, 80.25 percent of family members were literate, with a literacy index of 2.39. Based on landholding, all of the farmers fell into one of the three categories. Therefore, only small farmers liked mushroom growing, and the majority of farmers had an orchard. It has been determined that the farmer's primary source of revenue is the mushroom industry. In the case of the medium and large categories, mushrooms contributed the most to total farm income, accounting for 43.44 percent and 70.18 percent, respectively. Its overall contribution to farm revenue was found to be 49.42%. A mushroom producer makes more than \$30,000 a month from less than 500 bags of mushrooms, which is significantly more than the average Indian.

Keywords: Socioeconomics; mushroom farmers.

1. Introduction

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) has acknowledged mushrooms as food items that contribute to the protein nutrient in the diet of developing nations like India, where there is a high dependence on cereal diets. The noteworthy characteristic of mushrooms is that this filling and delicious food is grown entirely from waste materials and transforms a variety of industrial and agricultural waste into the substrate that supports mushroom development. Since it needs a cool environment to flourish, it is mostly grown on hills. Modern growing technology has made it feasible to grow this mushroom year-round under environmentally controlled settings as well as seasonally under uncontrolled conditions. More than a hundred nations commercially cultivate edible mushrooms on varied scales and with various techniques. The global mushroom output is increasing at a rate of 6–7% per year. In India, commercial mushroom farming started in the late 1970s, but production and productivity have increased at an impressive rate. India's mushroom production is anticipated to increase to about

201088 tonnes at this time. The principal mushroom-producing states in India are Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Odisha, and Haryana.

The most common type continues to rule both the Indian and international markets: the button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*). It produces about 90% of the nation's total production, compared to a global proportion of about 40%. The majority of controlled and uncontrolled white button mushroom cultivation takes place in North India. Numerous seasonal growers produce button mushrooms during the winter, primarily in the Northern States and with a focus on populous places like Chandigarh and Delhi.

2. Materials And Methods

2.1 Selection of Study Area

The study's primary goal was to look at the socioeconomic circumstances of mushroom farmers and how much money mushrooms contributed to their overall income. It also attempted to characterise the many aspects of mushroom farming in the study area. As the second-largest producer of mushrooms in the State, the study was carried out in Chhattisgarh's Bilaspur district.

2.2 Selection of Sample

With assistance from the Department of Horticulture, Government of Chhattisgarh, and the spawn supplier, a comprehensive list of mushroom growers was created. For the purpose of gathering data, a sample of 60 mushroom growers was selected at random from the list of growers.

2.3 Stratification of Sample Households

The cumulative cube root frequency approach was employed for stratum construction [7]. All mushroom farmers were divided into three groups based on the quantity of bags for the purpose of data analysis: Small Group

(300), Medium Group (301–500), and Large Group (> 500). The distribution of the mushroom growers who were sampled based on how many bags they had. It was discovered that 45% of farmers were small farmers with an average of 316 bags per grower and 0.63 hectares of land under cultivation, 38% of farmers were medium farmers with an average of 952 bags per farm and 1.03 hectares under cultivation, and 16.7% of farmers were large mushroom growers with an average of 2910 bags and 0.86 hectares under cultivation.

Table 1. Farm category-wise distribution of sampled households in the study area

Category of farmers	No. of Mushroom Bags	No of farmers	Percentage of farmers	Average No of bags	Average landholding size (Ha)
Small	≤300	27	45.00	316	0.63
Medium	301-500	23	38.33	952	1.03
Large	>500	10	16.67	2910	0.86
Total		60	100.00	992	0.82

2.4 Analytical Tools

The straightforward tabular method was used to compile and analyse the acquired data. Average calculations have been used to display the findings.

Following formulae/expressions were used for estimation of different parameters:

2.5 Tabular Analysis

The sample farmers' socioeconomic position

$$\text{Sex Ratio} = \frac{\text{No. of females in a family}}{\text{No. of males}} \times 1000$$

2.7 Literacy Rate

When evaluating the quality of human resources, literacy is a key metric that was calculated by subtracting the population of non-school-going children under the age of five from the entire sampled population.

$$\text{Literacy rate} = \frac{\text{Total no. of a literate person}}{\text{Total population} - \text{population below 5 years}} \times 100$$

2.8 Literacy Index

Literacy Index is calculated by the sum of the weighted value for literacy category (primary, middle, matric, senior secondary and graduate & above) to the number of persons to be literate.

$$\text{Literacy index} = \frac{\sum W_i X_i}{\sum X_i}$$

Where,

W_i = Weights (0, 1,2,3,4 and 5) for illiterate, primary, middle, matric, secondary and graduate & above respectively.

X_i = Number of persons in respective category.

$$\text{Dependency ratio w. r. t. total workers} = \frac{\text{No. of dependents in a family}}{\text{Total workers}}$$

was examined using a tabular format. The following formulas were used to calculate the sex ratio, literacy rate, and index:

2.6 Sex Ratio

Sex ratio represents the number of females per thousand males and was calculated for the total sampled households with the following formula:

2.9 Cropping Intensity

The cropping intensity has been worked out as the ratio of gross cropped area to the net sown area, expressed in percentage.

$$\text{Cropping intensity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Gross cropped area}}{\text{Net sown area}} \times 100$$

3. Results And Discussion

3.1 Socio-economic Characters of Sampled Farmers

This section discusses the various socioeconomic traits of mushroom farmers, such as their family size and composition, level of education, and occupation.

3.1.1 Size and structure of family

In Table 2, the size and makeup of the sampled homes in the study region have been determined. The table's analysis reveals that the nuclear family system was found to be more prevalent in the investigated households. The sampled mushroom growers' average family size was found to be 5.26 people per household. The number of females per thousand of males ranged between 690 in the case of a large farmer to 1062 in medium farmer with an average of 897 females per thousand of a male at an overall level.

3.1.2 Age-wise distribution of farmers

Age is seen as a significant socioeconomic

component that affects a person's ability to make decisions. Age also provides insight on a person's financial and educational potential. Therefore, an effort was made to gain insight into the age distribution of mushroom growers in the study locations represented in Table 2. All of the mushroom farmers were 44 years old on average. It demonstrates that the majority of growers are young people who run their businesses using modern technologies.

3.1.3 Literacy status

Education has a significant role in the process of growth. Table 2 summarises the examination of the general educational status of the sampled farm families and the head of the family. It was discovered that every mushroom farmer in the sample was literate. More than 20% of growers were graduates, 23.3% had completed their senior secondary education, and 20% had graduated from high school.

Table 2. Socio-economic characteristics of sample mushroom growers

	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1. Size and structure of the family	Number of the Family	27	23	10	60
	Joint family (%)	7.41	21.74	10	13.33
	Nuclear family (%)	92.6	78.26	90	86.67
	Average size of family	4.90	5.82	4.90	5.26
	sex ratio	833	1062	690	897
2. Age group of respondent	Below 30 Years	7.41	26.09	-	13.33
	30-40 years	33.3	30.43	40.00	33.33
	40 - 50 Years	25.9	17.39	40.00	25.00
	50 above	33.3	26.09	20.00	28.33
	Average age of respondent	46	41	45	44
3. Education	Primary	25.9	4.35	-	13.33
	Middle	25.9	13.04	30.00	21.67
	Metric	18.5	21.74	20.00	20.00
	Senior secondary	14.8	39.13	10.00	23.33
	Graduate	14.8	21.74	40.00	21.67
	Literacy rate (%)	88.8	85.27	93.62	88.25
	Literacy index	2.66	2.58	3.00	2.69
4. Occupational Pattern	Agriculture	85.6	85.42	85.00	85.34
	Service	8.25	9.38	5.00	8.23
	Business	6.19	5.21	10.00	6.43
	Average workers (No.)	3.60	4.17	4.00	3.89
5. Work force	Average No. of workers	3.60	4.17	4.00	3.89

		(73.50)	(71.64)	(81.63)	(74.14)
	Average No. of dependents	1.30	1.65	0.9	1.37
		(26.50)	(28.36)	(18.37)	(25.86)
	Average family size (No.)	4.90	5.82	4.90	5.26
		(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)
	Dependency ratio w. r. t. Total workers	0.36	0.40	0.23	0.35

Table 2 shows that the overall literacy rate was observed at 88.25 per cent which varied from

85.27 to 91.62 per cent among different categories. This highlights the fact that the literacy rate in the study areas is higher, but the quality of education is poor as indicated by the low literacy index.

3.1.4 Occupational distribution

The data shows that, overall, farming accounted for 85.34 percent of the workforce in the research area, making it the most common occupation. Public and private service sectors employed 8.23 and 6.43 percent of workers, respectively, while 6.43 percent owned their own businesses.

3.1.5 Workforce

Large farmers had the largest percentage of active workers (81.63%), followed by small farmers (73.48%), and medium farmers (71.64%). It was anticipated that people between the ages of 15 and 65 would be actively employed in productive economic pursuits and referred to as members of the active workforce. Medium-sized farms had the highest dependents, while large farms had the lowest. It was discovered that the overall reliance ratio for all workers was 0.35, and within the various groups.

3.2 Existing Resource Structure

This section discusses the current resource structure, which includes things like land, cropping patterns, livestock, farm investments, etc. Below are results broken down by category in various categories:

3.2.1 Land use pattern

In an agrarian economy, the land is a fundamental resource. An essential factor that directly impacts the income, consumption, saving, and investment of the sampled households is the size of the landholding. Small landholdings, particularly in rural areas, have a special significance in determining the opportunities for income generation. Examining the land use pattern is therefore important from both the perspective of the overall welfare and the rural economy.

The type of farming system in a region is determined by the land use pattern. In section 1.3, sampled farmers' land use patterns for mushroom producers are compiled by category. According to the data, small and large category mushroom growers had less than one hectare of land, which means that, according to landholding categories, they are considered marginal farmers. This finding suggests that, as education levels increased, these farmers chose to diversify in order to increase their farm income and standard of living. On a category-wide basis, 0.82 hectares was found to be the average size of landholding, of which 86.02 percent was used for agriculture. Large farmers had the highest percentage of land under orchard, followed by small and medium farmers. The area under orchard was found to be 64.73 percent. It was calculated how much of the land was pastures or uncultivated land (2.25%), forest land (6.59%), area for non-agricultural use (4.06%), and area for the mushroom house (0.82%). Almost the same trends were seen in all of the major categories. The total operational area ranged from 80.91 to 93.02 percent among the various mushroom farm classifications. It was discovered that the average holding size for the small, medium, and large categories was 0.63, 1.03, and 0.86 hectares, respectively.

3.2.2 Cropping pattern

Any region's cropping pattern is primarily influenced by the soil, height, microclimate, resources that are available, and management variables. The level of agricultural diversification in the selected farms is revealed by variations in the percent share of area under various crops in the gross cropped area.

Table 4 shows the findings from an analysis of the sampled farms' cropping patterns. The table clearly shows that little mushroom producers (126.86%), medium mushroom growers (124.26%), and large mushroom growers (122.00%) had the maximum cropping intensity. It was calculated to be 125.05 percent on a global scale, indicating

room for improvement in farm productivity. Due to the fact that fruit crops accounted for more than 60% of the total planted area, lower cropping intensity was also observed.

However, if only the cultivated land used for field crops is taken into account, cropping intensity is only 1.97 percent.

Table 3 . Land use pattern of selected mushroom growers (Area in hectare)

Land use Classes	Farm Size			
	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
Average Cultivated Area other than Orchard Area	0.15	0.20	0.18	0.18
	(24.07)	(19.59)	(20.47)	(21.28)
Irrigated	0.06	0.12	0.11	0.09
	(10.17)	(11.49)	(13.02)	(11.30)
Unirrigated	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.08
	(13.9)	(8.11)	(7.44)	(9.98)
Average Orchard Area	0.41	0.63	0.62	0.53
	(65.53)	(61.32)	(72.56)	(64.73)
Irrigated	0.24	0.49	0.22	0.33
	(38.53)	(47.64)	(26.05)	(40.73)
Unirrigated	0.17	0.14	0.40	0.20
	(27.00)	(11.99)	(46.51)	(23.19)
Total operational area	0.56	0.83	0.80	0.71
	(89.6)	(80.91)	(93.02)	(86.02)
Area under forest tree	0.04	0.09	0.02	0.05
	(6.62)	(8.28)	(1.86)	(6.59)
Pastures land / uncultivated land	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.02
	(1.89)	(3.55)	(0.93)	(2.52)
Area under non-agricultural use	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.03
	(1.51)	(6.68)	(1.86)	(4.06)
Area under mushroom bags	0.002	0.01	0.02	0.01
	(0.38)	(0.58)	(2.33)	(0.82)
Total area	0.63	1.03	0.86	0.82
	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)

Figure in parentheses are percentage to the average total area

Table 4. Farm Category wise cropping pattern (in hectare)

Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
Kharif crop				
Tomato	0.07	0.073	0.08	0.073
	(9.82)	(7.11)	(8.2)	(8.31)
Capsicum	0.046	0.052	0.016	0.043
	(6.45)	(5.06)	(1.64)	(4.90)
Beans	0.018	0.01	0.008	0.013
	(2.52)	(0.97)	(0.82)	(1.48)
Ginger	0.018	0.059	0.072	0.043
	(2.52)	(5.74)	(7.38)	(4.9)
Maize	-	0.007	-	0.003
		(0.68)		(0.34)
Rabi crops				
Wheat	0.01	0.003	-	0.006
	(1.4)	(0.29)		(0.68)
Pea	0.043	0.057	0.08	0.055
	(6.03)	(5.55)	(8.20)	(6.26)
Cauliflower	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.03
	(3.65)	(4.58)	(1.64)	(3.76)
Garlic	0.071	0.094	0.08	0.081
	(9.96)	(9.15)	(8.2)	(9.23)
Fruit	0.411	0.632	0.624	0.531

	(57.64)	(61.54)	(63.93)	(60.48)
Gross cropped area	0.713	1.027	0.976	0.878
	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)

Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
Net sown area	0.56	0.83	0.80	0.71
Cropping intensity	126.86	124.26	122.00	125.05

Figure in parentheses are percentage to total gross cropped area

Table 5. Farm category wise average income composition of sampled households (Amount in Rupees)

Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
Kharif crops	46500.00	67626.09	64850.00	57656.67
	(6.66)	(4.97)	(2.43)	(4.50)
Rabi crops	29993.15	40998.91	34402.50	34946.92
	(4.30)	(3.01)	(1.29)	(2.73)
Fruits	336681.50	546113.00	542120.00	451203.30
	(48.23)	(40.14)	(20.29)	(35.22)
Mushroom	189302.80	591100.00	1928780.00	633237.90
	(27.12)	(43.44)	(72.18)	(49.42)
Service/Business	95555.56	114782.60	102000.00	104000.00
	(13.69)	(8.44)	(3.82)	(8.12)
Total	698033.00	1360621.00	2672153.00	1281218.00
	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)	(100.00)

3.3 Income Structure

Number in parenthesis represents a percentage of the total.

Mushroom farming is a lucrative food industry [8]. According to socioeconomic metrics, the majority of

Table 5 presents the source-wise family income breakdown of the various kinds of sampled mushroom farms in order to illustrate the relative relevance of mushroom growing in the economy of the studied households. The data shows that at the overall level of sampled mushroom growers, or based on the average crops of 2.33 taken by the grower in a year, fruits were the next largest contributor to family income, at 35.22 percent, followed by Kharif crops at 4.50 percent and rabi crops at 2.73 percent.

Between small and large farmers, the percentage of income from mushrooms in total income ranged from 27.12 to 72.18 percent, demonstrating a higher income contribution with an increase in the number of bags produced. More than 72% of the total income for major mushroom producers was calculated to come from the sale of mushrooms, indicating that this is their primary source of income.

5. Conclusion

Despite being one of the only large-scale commercial applications of microbial technology for the bioconversion of agricultural and forestry waste materials to

the sample houses of nuclear families, mushroom farming is still regarded as an accessory agribusiness industry in India. Although family size and the gender split do not influence the adoption of mushroom production, farmers may be encouraged to grow mushrooms if they are literate. The farmers were all literate, as were the majority of their families. Studying households' literacy levels revealed that, on average, 88.25 percent of family members were literate, with a literacy index of 2.69.

According to the occupational distribution, farming is practised by 85.34 percent of the workforce in the households under study, while 8.23 percent and 6.43 percent of the workforce, respectively, work in the public and private sectors of services and own their own businesses. This essentially means that growing mushrooms is best left to farmers.

The total workforce for all mushroom producers was 74.14 percent; among the various categories, it was discovered that the large category (81.63%) reported the highest percentage of active workers and the medium category (71.64%) the lowest. The calculated overall dependency ratio, or 0.35, shows that, on average, one worker must support less than one family member.

Based on landholding, all of the farmers fell into one of the three categories. Therefore, only small farmers preferred mushroom growing, and the majority of farmers owned

orchards. On average, 64.73 percent of the total holding was found to be dedicated to orchards.

It has been determined that the farmer's primary source of revenue is the mushroom industry. In the case of the medium and large categories, mushrooms contributed the most to total farm income, accounting for 43.44 percent and 72.18 percent, respectively. Its overall contribution to farm income was found to be 49.42%. A mushroom producer makes more than \$30,000 per month from less than 500 bags of mushrooms, which is significantly more than the average Indian.

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